

RISK ASSESSMENT OF DIABETES MELLITUS USING INDIAN DIABETIC RISK SCORE IN TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL; A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY

Channabasappagouda Subedar^{*1}, S. Deepthi², Ranjeeta Joshi², Alby Alex²

^{*1,2}Pharm D Intern, RMES's College of Pharmacy, Kalaburagi.

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*Corresponding Author

Channabasappagouda Subedar

Pharm D. Intern, RMES's College
of Pharmacy, Kalaburagi.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder of multiple etiologies characterized by chronic hyperglycemia with disturbance of carbohydrate, protein and fat metabolism resulting from impaired insulin secretion, insulin action or both. Diabetes is an insidious public health problem. It has emerged as a global pandemic of the 21st century. This study aimed to assess the risk developing Diabetes Mellitus by utilizing the simplified Indian Diabetes Risk Score (IDRS), a screening instrument established in 2005 by Dr.Mohan and MDRF (Madras diabetes research foundation). **Objective:** The main objective of our study is to assess the risk of developing diabetes using IDRS in a tertiary care teaching hospital. **Methodology:** A cross sectional study was conducted among 310 study participants for a period of 6 months. The level of risk for diabetes was assessed by Indian Diabetic Risk Score.

IDRS includes four parameters consisting of Age, Abdominal obesity, Physical activity and Family history. The results were analysed by using microsoft excel sheet. **Result:** Among 328 patients, the majority of them 182(55.5%) were males and 146(44.5%) were females. IDRS categorization revealed that 138(42.1%) belonged to high risk, 118 (36.0%) belonged to moderate risk, 72(22.0%) belonged to low risk for developing diabetes mellitus. **Conclusion:** The study showed that 42.1% of participant were at high DM risk due to factors like age, waist circumference and low activity. Clinical pharmacists are vital for counseling on the disease, medication and lifestyle.

KEYWORDS: IDRS, Diabetes Mellitus, MDRF.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is an insidious public health problem. It has emerged as a global pandemic of the 21st century.^[1]

Its burden is on the rise among all the age groups affecting urban and rural population without urban and rural differences.^[2]

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder of multiple etiologies characterized by chronic hyperglycemia with disturbance of carbohydrate, protein and fat metabolism resulting from impaired insulin secretion, insulin action or both.^[3]

The etiology of Diabetes in Indian population is multifactorial and it mainly includes genetic factors (HLA genes) coupled with environmental influences such as obesity associated with rising living standards, steady urban migration and lifestyle changes.^[4]

The rising prevalence of diabetes and other non-communicable diseases is attributed to a combination of factors - unhealthy diet, rapid urbanization, tobacco use, sedentary lifestyles, and increasing life expectancy.^[5]

Obesity has been consistently associated with high prevalence and incidence of lifestyle disease. Measuring a person's waist circumference is a simplest way to assess central obesity.^[6]

Sedentary lifestyle, work pressure, increasing stress amongst individuals are well known factors in the causation of diabetes.^[7]

People with IGT (impaired glucose tolerance) or IFG (impaired fasting glucose) and gestational diabetics are at high risk of progressing to type 2 diabetes, all thought this is not inevitable.^[8]

Diabetes is one of the contender disease for which the community can be screened as it qualifies criteria of having a long latent asymptomatic stage that may be present for up to 7 years before diagnosis, is treatable, and testing is acceptable to patients. Early identification of the individuals at risk of developing diabetes would help in taking appropriate intervention in the form of dietary changes and increasing physical activity, thus helping to prevent, or

least delay, onset of diabetes.

Early identification of the patient can be strengthened by mass screening camps for the general public.^[10]

Hence, identification of at- risk individuals is extremely important to prevent diabetes in India.^[9]

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Duration

The study has been carried out for a period of Six month (March-August 2024)

Study Design

Hospital based cross sectional study.

Study Site

The study has been conducted at department of general medicine, gulbarga institute of medical science.

Source of Data

Patient case sheets

Indian Diabetic Risk Score Scale Leaflet will be prepared

Inclusion Criteria

Patient of both sex Age ≥ 35 years

Patients willing to sign inform consent form Undiagnosed diabetic patients with other comorbidity

Exclusion Criteria

Patients diagnosed with Diabetes Mellitus Patients with gestational diabetes

Patient with abdominal distension

Patient who are not willing to sign inform consent form

RESULTS

1. GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS

In the present study we have enrolled 328 participants during study period. Out of which 186(55.5%) were males and 142(45.5%) were females.

Table 1: gender wise distribution of participants.

GENDER	NO OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE
MALE	186	55.5%
FEMALE	142	45.5%
TOTAL	328	100%

2. AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS

Among 328 participants 142 were <35 years(43.3%), 122 were between 36-49 years(37.2%) and 64 were \geq 50 years(19.5%).

Figure 1: age wise distribution of participants.

3. IDRS SCALE AMONG STUDY PARTICIPANTS

In our study, The IDRS includes Age, Abdominal obesity, Physical activity and family history. Among 206 study participants 55 (26.6%) were aged<35 years, 69 (33.4%) were aged 35-49 years, 82 (40%) were aged \geq 50 years.

93 (45%) had a Waist circumference of<80cm (female) OR <90cm (male), 76 (37%) had a Waist circumference of >80-89cm (female) OR >90-99cm (male), 37(18%) had a Waist circumference of >90cm (female) OR >100cm (male).

44 (21.3%) were doing regular exercise and strenuous work, 94 (45.6%) were on irregular/moderate exercise, while 68 (33.0%) of them had no physical activity.

Only 1 (0.4%) study participant had a positive family history of both parents, 22 (10.6%) had either of parents, 183 (89%) had no family history

Table 2: IDRS scale among study participants.

		IDRS SCORE	NO OF SAMPLE	PERCENTAGE OF SAMPLE
AGE	<35	0	142	43.3%
	36-49	20	122	37.2%
	≥50	30	64	19.5%
ABDOMINAL OBESITY	Waist <80cm(female) <90cm(male)	0	150	45.8%
	Waist >80-89cm(female)>90-99cm(male)	10	96	29.2%
	Waist >90cm(female)>100cm (male)	20	82	25%
PHYSICAL ACTIVITY	Exercise + strenuous work	0	30	9.2%
	Exercise(irregular)or strenuous work	20	278	84.8%
	No exercise and sedentary work	30	20	6.1%
FAMILY HISTORY	NO Family History	0	169	51.5%
	Either parent	10	110	33.5%
	Both parent	20	49	14.9%

Figure 2: distribution of participants according to age.

Figure 3: distribution of participants according to abdominal obesity.

Figure 4: distribution of participants according to physical activity.

Figure 5: distribution of participants according to family history.

4. RISK WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS

Among 328 participants 138 were at very high risk(42.0%), 118 were at moderate risk(36.0%), 72 were at low risk(22%).

Table 3: risk wise distribution of participants.

SCORE	NO OF SAMPLE	PERCENTAGE OF SAMPLE
≥60 VERY HIGH RISK	138	42.0%
30-50 MODERATE RISK	118	36.0%
<30 LOW RISK	72	22%
TOTAL	328	100%

Figure 6: risk wise distribution of participants.

DISCUSSION

Diabetes Mellitus is one of the most common non communicable disease globally. It is one of the most important leading cause of death in most high income countries. It is an insidious public health problem that has emerged as global pandemic of 21st century. India has the unfortunate privilege of being called the “Diabetic capital of world”. In this study we used IDRS to assess the risk development of diabetes mellitus. IDRS is a useful tool to identify high risk individuals who can be targeted for the annual screening for diabetes. IDRS requires four risk factors like age, abdominal obesity, level of physical activity and family history of diabetes. In our study, we had a sample size of 328 participants, out of which 182 were males(55.5%) and 146 were females(44.5%). Males were predominant than females in this study. In our study out of 328 participants, 138 were at high risk(42.1%), 118 were at moderate risk(36.0%), 72 were at low risk(22.0%). This is similar with Shaily Dandona et.al., who conducted a study on 1533 participants out of which 749(48.7%) were at high risk,

734(47.8%) were at moderate risk, 54(3.5%) were at low risk. In our study we found that, increased risk for diabetes was seen with the advancement of age, we included the participants of age ≥ 18 years. Among 328 participants, 64 (19.5%) were aged more than 50years, 122(37.2%) were in the age group of 35-49years and 142 (43.3%) were found to be < 35 years. This is similar with Chowdhury Ranadip, who conducted a study on 50 participants, of which 111(47.2%) were in the age group 20-34years, 67(28.5%) were in the age group of 35-49years and 57 (24.3%) were ≥ 50 years. Waist circumference is an indicator of abdominal obesity and this is one of the major risk factor for Diabetis Mellitus. In the present study we found a total of 138 participants, out of 328 having waist ≥ 90 cm (female), ≥ 100 cm (male). Out of which 66, majority were found to have higher risk for developing Diabetes Mellitus. This is synonymous with the study conducted by P. K. S. S. Usha Sri et.al. Even though 17 participants had a waist circumference of < 80 cm (female), < 90 cm (male), were at high risk of developing diabetes. In an obese patient, there is an increased circulating free fatty acids, adipocytokines (necrosis factor- α , Interleukin-6 etc.) contribute to insulin resistance which is a leading factor for diabetes mellitus. In the present study, among 328 participants, 20 were found to have no physical activity, out of which 14 were at high risk of developing Diabetes Mellitus. There are three primary benefits of physical activity on the delay of diabetes mellitus:

- 1) contraction of SKM induces an increase in blood flow into the muscles, enhancing glucose uptake from plasma.
- 2) Physical activity, reduces the notorious intra-abdominal fat, which is a known risk factor that promote insulin resistance.
- 3) Moderate intensity exercise has been shown to improve glucose uptake by 40%.

In the present study, among 328 participants, 49(14.9%) were at high risk with positive family history of both parents, 110(33.5%) were at moderate risk with positive family history of either parents and 169(51.5%) were at lower risk of no family history. In the study conducted by P.K.S.S Usha Sri et.al., shows majority 110(55%) of the population had a negative family history.

CONCLUSION

we conclude that, IDRS is a very useful and effective tool for the identification of undiagnosed DM .In our study, 138(42.1%) study participants were under high risk of developing DM. Increasing age, waist circumference, low physical activity, positive family

history were found to be major risk factor, for developing of Diabetes.

Use of alcohol and smoking were also associated with risk of developing Diabetes Mellitus. Early detection of development of diabetes can be helpful in its management. A clinical pharmacist plays a vital role in the patient counselling about the disease, medication and life style modification which enhances the patient's knowledge about their disease state and medication usage.

The early stage of Diabetes can be managed by life style modification. Thereby, the burden of the diabetes can be reduced at the earliest.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

All the authors have contributed equally.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

ETHICS DECLARATION

The Institutional Ethics Committee at RMES's College of Pharmacy approved the protocol. All residents in the hospital provided informed consent.

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

All authors have consented to the publication of their work.

COMPETING INTERESTS

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